

Fluoberyllates of Trivalent Metals :

II. Aluminium Alums

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Feigl and Chaeffer² observed that AlF_6^{3-} ion responds to the test of Al^{3+} ion in presence of beryllium. This fact together with the solubility of CaF_2 in solutions containing beryllium ions clearly points to the greater stability of BeF_4^{2-} over AlF_6^{3-} ion. Actually, beryllium fluoride also exists in aqueous solution as beryllium fluoberyllate³. Thus, $\text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3$ is a stable substance the preparation and properties of which have already been described⁴. In our previous communication⁴ we have reported the isolation of $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{BeF}_4$, $\text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and K_2BeF_4 , $\text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$. At present we have isolated the other alums of the series. Attempts are also being made to isolate the alums with trivalent metals like iron, chromium, titanium etc. which will be published in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Methods of analysis: Alkali metals were estimated as their sulfates after evaporating off fluorine with conc. H_2SO_4 and precipitating Beryllium and Aluminium with 2% solution of oxine in ammoniacal medium.

Aluminium was determined as Alumina.

Fluoberyllate was determined as barium fluoberyllate at $\text{pH} = 4$.

In the determination of Thallium in thallos alum, BeF_4^{2-} was first precipitated as BaBeF_4 with 5% barium nitrate solution, aluminium was precipitated as $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ and filtered off, then in the filtrate thallium was precipitated as Tl_2CrO_4 with 10% solution of K_2CrO_4 and estimated as such.

Hydrazine was determined with iodine in a buffered medium (buffered with Rochelle salt) and excess iodine was back titrated with standard thiosulfate solution.

Hydroxylamine was estimated with bromate-bromide mixture in acidic medium and excess bromate was determined iodometrically.

1. To whom all communications regarding this publication should be addressed.
2. F. Feigl and A. Chaeffer, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 23, 351.
3. A. K. Boral, H. K. Saha and N. Ray, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, 29, 2490-2494.
4. A. K. Boral, H. K. Saha and N. Ray, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1968, 45, 90.

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

Fluoberyllic acid : Fluoberyllic acid was prepared according to the method of Ray et al⁵.

Aluminium fluoberyllate was prepared exactly in the same way as described in a previous communication⁴.

Determination of densities : Densities were determined by floatation of alum crystals using suitable mixtures of liquids like methylene iodide and benzene. The results are given in gms./c.c. in table I.

TABLE I

Alums	Density gm/cc. at 30°	Solubilities gms. per cent		
		0°	10°	30°
(NH ₄) ₂ BeF ₄ . Al ₂ (BeF ₄) ₃ . 24H ₂ O	1.923	3.66	5.95	10.14
K ₂ BeF ₄ . Al ₂ (BeF ₄) ₃ . 24H ₂ O	2.058	4.12	6.42	11.03
Rb ₂ BeF ₄ . Al ₂ (BeF ₄) ₃ . 24H ₂ O	2.140	0.82	1.16	2.28
Cs ₂ BeF ₄ . Al ₂ (BeF ₄) ₃ . 24H ₂ O	2.22	0.29	0.37	0.74

Determination of solubilities : Solubilities were determined at different temperatures after the saturated solution in contact with the solid phase attained equilibrium. The components were then estimated by usual procedure. The results are expressed in gms. per cent. and given in Table I.

Fluoberyllate-Rubidium alum ; Rb₂BeF₄. Al₂(BeF₄)₃. 24H₂O : A sample of 0.256 gm. of Rubidium fluoberyllate in solution was mixed with 0.633 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution i.e., in molecular proportion of 1:1, and kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals obtained were examined under microscope and were found to be octahedral in shape. A sample of 0.2802 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.2635 gm. of BaBeF₄ and 0.0312 gm. of Al₂O₃. A sample of 0.1470 gm. of the material gave 0.0380 gm. of Rb₂SO₄.

Found, Al, 5.89% ; BeF₄²⁻, 35.95% ; Rb, 17.20%.

Calculated for Rb₂BeF₄. Al₂(BeF₄)₃. 24H₂O ;

Al, 5.72% ; BeF₄²⁻, 36.06% ; Rb, 17.14%.

Fluoberyllate-Caesium Alum : Cs₂BeF₄. Al₂(BeF₄)₃. 24H₂O : An aqueous solution of 0.35 gm. of caesium fluoberyllate was mixed with 0.63 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in solution and crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape. A sample of 0.1924 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.1539 gm. of BaBeF₄ and 0.0188 gm. of Al₂O₃. 0.1284 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.0383 gm. of Cs₂SO₄.

Found : Al, 5.17% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 30.56% and Cs = 23.69% ;

Calculated for $\text{Cs}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$;

Al, 4.24% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 31.14% ; Cs, 24.36%.

Fluoberyllate-Thallos alum : $\text{Tl}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous solution of 0.49 gm. of thallos fluoberyllate was mixed with 0.63 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in solution and crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape. The crystals effloresce readily and lose their crystal shape. A sample of 0.1472 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.1054 gm. of BaBeF_4 , 0.0116 gm. of Al_2O_3 . A sample of 0.2238 gm. of the material gave 0.0939 gm. of Ti_2CrO_4 .

Found : Tl, 32.69% ; Al, 4.17% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 27.30% ;

Calculated for, $\text{Tl}_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

Tl, 33.09% ; Al, 4.37% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 27.54%.

Fluoberyllate-Hydrazine alum : $(\text{N}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous solution of 0.30 gm. of normal hydrazine fluoberyllate was mixed with 1.26 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution. The solution was then slightly acidified with fluoberyllic acid. The pH of the solution was between 3 to 4. This was kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals obtained, on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape.

The crystals effloresce readily and the loss in weight corresponds to the loss of nine molecules of water on keeping in a desiccator over silica gel. With the loss in water molecule the crystal shape is also lost.

A sample of 0.1274 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.1285 gm. of BaBeF_4 and 0.0139 gm. of Al_2O_3 .

0.0246 gm. of the material consumed 18.8 ml. of $0.2372 \frac{\text{N}}{20}$ Iodine solution.

Found : N_2H_4 , 7.38% ; Al, 5.78% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 38.56% ;

Calculated for, $(\text{N}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

N_2H_4 , 7.17% ; Al, 6.04% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 38.03%.

Fluoberyllate-Tetramethylammonium alum : $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4]_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

An aqueous solution of 0.46 gm. of tetramethylammonium fluoberyllate was mixed with 1.26 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution and crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape. The crystals effloresce slowly and the loss in water corresponds to the loss of nine molecules of water on keeping in a desiccator over silica gel. The crystal shape is gradually lost with the loss in water molecules.

A sample of 0.2230 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.2074 gm. of BaBeF_4 and 0.0241 gm. of Al_2O_3 .

Found : Al, 5.72% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 34.55% ;

Calculated for, $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2]\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$,

Al, 5.54% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 34.88% ;

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method :

Found : N, 2.84% ; Calculated, 2.87%.

Hydroxylamine fluoberyllate : $(\text{NH}_3\text{OH})_2\text{BeF}_4$: About 2 gm. of Thallous fluoberyllate in aqueous solution was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in aqueous solution, slowly drop by drop with constant stirring. Precipitation of thallous chloride being complete, hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added in slight excess. Precipitated thallous chloride was filtered off and the filtrate was kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid for crystallisation. The product obtained was recrystallised thrice to get pure product.

0.1526 gm. of the substance on analysis gave 0.0259 gm. of BeO and 0.1540 gm. of CaF_2 .

Found : Be, 6.11% ; F, 49.14%

Calculated for $(\text{NH}_3\text{OH})_2\text{BeF}_4$; Be, 5.88% ; F, 49.67%.

Fluoberyllate-hydroxylamine alum : $(\text{NH}_3\text{OH})_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$. 0.31 gm. of hydroxylamine fluoberyllate in aqueous solution was mixed with 1.26 gm. of aluminium fluoberyllate in aqueous solution. The solution was slightly acidified with fluoberyllic acid. pH of the solution was in between 3 to 4. This was then crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulfuric acid. The crystals on examination under microscope were found to be octahedral in shape. The crystals are hygroscopic, absorbs moisture from the atmosphere and changes into a gummy mass within 3 to 4 days. A sample of 0.1246 gm. of the material on analysis gave 0.1237 gm. of BaBeF_4 and 0.0129 gm. of Al_2O_3 .

Found : Al, 5.48% ; BeF_4^{2-} , 37.96% ;

Calculated for, $(\text{NH}_3\text{OH})_2\text{BeF}_4 \cdot \text{Al}_2(\text{BeF}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Al, 6.04% ;

BeF_4^{2-} , 38.03%.

Found : NH_3OH , 7.34% ; Calculated, 7.38%.

Further work in this line including X-ray investigations and thermogravimetric analysis are in progress which will be published later on.